

PAPER • OPEN ACCESS

Measurement of flow deflection effects around an offshore wind farm caused by global blockage

To cite this article: Jörg Schneemann *et al* 2025 *J. Phys.: Conf. Ser.* **3016** 012012

View the [article online](#) for updates and enhancements.

You may also like

- [How do wind farm blockage and axial induction control interact?](#)
Ervin Bossanyi and James Bleeg
- [Investigation of the nacelle blockage effect for a downwind turbine](#)
Benjamin Anderson, Emmanuel Branlard, Ganesh Vijayakumar *et al.*
- [Numerical simulations over a three body launch vehicle for incompressible flows](#)
D Siva Krishna Reddy, Sagar Gupta and Mayank Yadav

UNITED THROUGH SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY

 The Electrochemical Society
Advancing solid state & electrochemical science & technology

**248th
ECS Meeting**
Chicago, IL
October 12-16, 2025
Hilton Chicago

**Science +
Technology +
YOU!**

**Register by
September 22
to save \$\$**

REGISTER NOW

Measurement of flow deflection effects around an offshore wind farm caused by global blockage

Jörge Schneemann^{1,2}, Frauke Theuer^{1,2}, Andreas Rott^{1,2}, Martin Kühn^{1,2}

¹Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg, School of Mathematics and Science, Institute of Physics

²ForWind - Center for Wind Energy Research, Kükersweg 70, 26129 Oldenburg, Germany

E-mail: j.schneemann@uol.de

Abstract. The Global-Blockage Effect, i. e. the accumulated induction zone of a whole wind farm, can reduce upstream wind speeds and is expected to deflect the incoming wind upwards and sideways. While wind speed deficits were observed in free field experiments, there is no experimental evidence for global blockage induced diverging flows and their strengths in front of large wind farms. We aim for the experimental confirmation of flow deflections to the sides of a wind farm due to global blockage. We analyse long-range scanning lidar data in the inflow of a large offshore wind farm for diverging wind directions. In a previous study we detected global blockage induced velocity deficits using the same data set. We found significant local flow direction differences in the sectors left and right of the stream-wise centre line of the wind farm indicating the flow to be deflected to the wind farm sides. We conclude that not only wind speed deficits but also wind direction changes are caused by the Global-Blockage Effect and both should be considered in accurate modelling.

1 Introduction

The accumulated blockage effect of the turbines in a wind farm decelerates the upstream flow and is expected to deflect it upwards and sideways [1]. This phenomenon is called the Global-Blockage Effect (GBE) and can influence the wind farm yield. The GBE came into the focus of research and industry in the last years since it must be considered for accurate wind farm performance assessment. In that context, experimental observations are urgently needed for GBE model validation. Aside inner farm wind turbine wakes and long reaching cluster wakes [2] GBE is another important large scale wind farm effect which should be considered in wind farm yield assessment.

Several numerical studies investigate the GBE in different wind farm and stability configurations, e.g. [3, 4, 5]. All these studies identify the onset of a continuous high-pressure region in front of the wind farm as the origin of the GBE. Furthermore, Gomez et al. show that a vertical displacement of the flow can be associated with the pressure increase approaching the wind farm [6]. Contrarily, experimental evidence for the GBE is rare so far. Compared to wake effects with wind speed differences in the order of metres per second distributed over short crosswise distances of some tens of metres, global blockage is much harder to detect. The effect appears over larger areas of some kilometres width and results in wind speed differences in the order of only few tenths of metres per second. Bleeg et al. used measurements at meteorological masts before and after the construction of wind farms and compared the data to reference masts to detect global blockage [7]. They found an average slowdown of 1.9% in the flow along an

upstream distance of seven to ten rotor diameters. Schneemann et al. used data from a scanning lidar to investigate the inflow of a large offshore wind farm [8]. They found evidence for global blockage in stable atmospheric conditions and the turbines operating at high thrust coefficients. Detected wind speed deficits were approximately 4% with an accuracy range of 2% to 6%. The comprehensive lidar measurement campaign within the industry-led research project GLoBE found evidence for the GBE with a deceleration in front of the farm and an acceleration in the farm, i.e. a redistributive effect on power within a wind farm. Further, recommendations for GBE modelling are given [9, 10, 11]. Hasager et al. analysed photographs of sea fog at an offshore wind farm in a special meteorological situation and conclude that the fog formation can plausibly be caused by the GBE [12]. These studies focus on detecting a wind speed reduction upstream and agree on the magnitude of the effect in the range of a single-digit percentage in stable stratification. The deflection of the flow upwards and to the sides of the wind farm has not been investigated experimentally so far. For a better understanding of GBE and the validation of GBE models, improved knowledge about the whole flow field including momentum transport around the farm, i.e. flow deflection, is needed.

The objective of this paper is to experimentally assess the existence and strength of the global blockage-induced flow deflection around a large offshore wind farm based on long-range lidar data. To achieve this goal we extend the analysis of an existing lidar data set [8] to find evidence for crosswise flow deflection.

2 Methods

This section provides an overview of the lidar measurement campaign in the offshore wind farm Global Tech I (GTI). Additional information on the campaign can be found in [2, 8]. This study uses the same lidar data subset in which Schneemann et al. found a GBE induced upstream wind speed deficit [8]. Further, this section introduces the lidar data analysis.

2.1 Wind farm and lidar measurements

The 400 MW offshore wind farm GTI is located in the German Bight and features 80 wind turbines AD 5-116 with rated power $P_r = 5$ MW, rotor diameter $D = 116$ m and hub height $h_h = 92$ m. A scanning long-range Doppler wind lidar Leosphere/Vaisala Windcube 200S (serial no. WLS200S-024) was installed on the access platform (transition piece, TP) of turbine GT58 in GTI at a height of approximately 24.6 m above mean sea level.

Figure 1 shows a map of the German North Sea, the layout of GTI, the lidar location and the sector measured by the lidar. We use lidar Plan Position Indicator (PPI) scans upstream of GTI in a southwesterly azimuth sector with 0° elevation, an acquisition time of 2.0 s, a scanning speed of $1^\circ/\text{s}$, 150° sector width, a resulting time per scan of 150 s and a maximum range of 7990 m. We consider data from a period between February 2019 and June 2019 and filtered for situations for which the wind farm was running at at least 50% of its rated power and 80% of its estimated power (see Sect. 2.4 in [8]). For these conditions we assume the wind turbines operating at the plateau region of the thrust coefficient curve. We use the same lidar data subset in stable stratification ($0 \text{ m} < L < 1000 \text{ m}$ with Obukhov length L) and turbines operating at a high thrust coefficient in which Schneemann et al. found a GBE induced upstream wind speed deficit [8]. The subset contains $N = 79$ scans in a wind speed range $8 \text{ m s}^{-1} \leq u \leq 11 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ with a mean wind speed $\bar{u}_{\text{GT58}} = 9.23 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, wind directions in the sector $250^\circ \leq \chi \leq 260^\circ$, a mean wind direction $\bar{\chi} = 256^\circ$ with a standard deviation of $\sigma_\chi = 2.78^\circ$ and a median Obukhov length of $L_{\text{med}} = 307 \text{ m}$ (see Sect. 3.4 and Fig. 7 in [8]).

2.2 Lidar data processing and uncertainty estimation

Lidar scans used for this analysis were filtered by means of a carrier-to-noise (CNR) threshold, with values $-26 \text{ dB} < \text{CNR} < 0 \text{ dB}$ considered valid. As a consequence of a thrust-dependent tilt of the lidar device as well as the curvature of the Earth, the measuring height varied within the scan and also changed dynamically with time [8, 13]. Thus, measurements were extrapolated to lidar height $z_{\text{TP}} = 24.6 \text{ m}$ using a stability corrected logarithmic wind speed profile [8]. A least squares Velocity Azimuth Display fit (VAD or cosine fit) to the lidar's line of sight wind speed measurements u_{los} over its azimuth angle ϑ was performed to determine the global horizontal wind speed and direction. Commonly, one assumes a homogeneous wind field for the VAD algorithm, i.e. a constant wind direction across the whole lidar scan. To be able to detect possible wind direction changes related to the occurrence of global blockage, we adjusted this procedure. First, we split each scan into range gate intervals r , which divide the range of the lidar from 500 m to 8000 m in 500 m increments. Second, we determined a global wind direction $\chi_{\text{global},r}$ for each r . This wind direction served as a reference to split the azimuth angles of the lidar ϑ for each r into a northerly part with $\vartheta > \chi_{\text{global},r}$ and a southerly one with $\vartheta < \chi_{\text{global},r}$. Figure 2 shows the

Figure 1: (a) Location of the wind farm GTI (orange) in the North Sea with neighbouring wind farms and clusters shown. Wind farms under construction are depicted as open shapes (status beginning of 2019). (b) Layout of GTI (• with turbine numbers). The position of the lidar on turbine GT58 (red filled \diamond) and the lidar scan region covering the area of the four different 150° scan sectors (red line) are highlighted. The turbine locations (small \times) and the substations (\times) of the wind farms Hohe See (southerly blue shape) and Albatros (northerly blue shape), which were under construction during the measurements, are marked (Figure adapted from [8]).

analysed lidar sector divided into the range intervals. In order to avoid overloading the figure, only one global wind direction and one wind direction for each of the northern and southern sectors are shown. However, it should be noted that these are determined separately for each range gate interval r . Third, we performed a VAD fit for each of the intervals, fixing the amplitude, i.e. wind speed, to the averaged line of sight wind speed measurements $\pm 2.5^\circ$ around the global wind direction. We overlapped the northerly and southerly regions by $\pm 10^\circ$ to allow for a smooth transition between the regions. We further selected azimuth sectors of the same size for both fits, i.e. neglected azimuth angles of the larger sector. From the wind direction in the south and north sector $\chi_{\text{sector},r}$ and the global wind direction $\chi_{\text{global},r}$ we derive the wind direction deviation $\Delta\chi_{\text{global},r} = \chi_{\text{sector},r} - \chi_{\text{global},r}$. We averaged $\Delta\chi_{\text{global},r}$ over all scans for each range gate interval r and calculated its respective standard error of the mean (SEM). Figure 3 shows an example of the VAD fit of line of sight wind speed over the azimuth angle to illustrate the methodology. The results of the VAD fit for the whole sector (black), the northerly (red) and southerly (blue) regions are shown.

3 Results

Figure 3 exemplarily indicates the divergence of the flow. The global fit to the whole sector finds the position of the maximum of the data points but the amplitude is clearly underestimated. The fit seems to be compressed due to the inhomogeneity of the flow. Both regional fits to the subsets of data find a shifted position of the maximum (i.e. wind direction) and well represent the maximal amplitude. In the particular opposite sector they proceed clearly off the data points.

Figure 4 summarizes the results of the range gate-dependent VAD fits. For each scan the difference between the range gate-dependent global wind direction and the northerly and southerly wind direction is determined and averaged over all analysed scans. The SEM is visualized as error bars. In the northerly sector of the scan the wind direction is generally smaller than on average for all available ranges up to 5500 m. In the southerly region it is generally larger. This means, that the wind directions in both sectors diverge towards the sides of the wind farm. For both the southerly and the northerly sector the difference to the mean wind directions becomes larger with increasing range gates, reaching values up to approximately 3° . The relatively narrow and non-overlapping error bars of approximately $\pm 0.5^\circ$ represent the uncertainty level and indicate the significance of the results.

Figure 2: Layout of wind farm GTI (black markers) with the position of the lidar on turbine GT58 (red marker) and the upstream part of the lidar scan region (red sector). The scan sector is grouped in range intervals r (red dashed radii) and divided (black dashed line) by the mean wind direction (red arrow) in a northerly sector N and a southerly sector S. Black arrows indicate the expected result of diverging flow directions for a GBE situation. A wind direction detection is performed on each range interval r in the N and S sector respectively (see Sect. 2.2).

As an additional check we applied the same methodology to the cases with lower thrust coefficients and unstable stratification for which we previously did not find any indication for GBE induced upstream wind speed reductions [8]. Applying the above mentioned methodology on these cases we found no significant differences in wind directions of southerly and northerly regions (not shown here).

4 Discussion

We performed an extended analysis of a lidar dataset used to identify an upstream GBE induced wind speed deficit at the offshore wind farm GTI [8]. We aimed for the experimental detection of a GBE induced horizontal flow divergence upstream indicated by a flow deflection towards the wind farm sides [1]. Aside the wind speed deficit shown in [8] we found diverging wind directions upstream of GTI. The wind direction difference to the global wind direction increased with distance from 750 m to 3750 m and stayed almost constant up to 5250 m in both the north and south sector (Figure 4). Here the wind direction difference was approximately $3^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$ towards the wind farm sides. The standard error of the mean indicates statistical significance of the results. Due to the deceleration caused by the GBE and the conservation of mass, we expected a divergent flow [1]. We observed the horizontal components of the sideways deflected flow in this work. From our single lidar measurements we can not further resolve the local wind directions in the upstream flow field to derive stream lines. Measurements with at least two lidars in a dual Doppler configuration, i.e. two locally measured horizontal flow components, could be used to better resolve wind directions in future studies.

An upwards directed flow deflection is further expected to occur but is not detectable with our horizontally pointing measurement setup. A vertically-staring lidar in front of a wind farm or in the first wind turbine row can possibly detect updraft in GBE situations in future analyses.

The increase in the detected wind direction difference with range we show in Figure 4 can be at least partially explained with the measurement geometry sketched in Figure 2. With increasing range the length of the arc sector scanned by the lidar and used for VAD wind direction detection increases. For

Figure 3: Exemplary lidar line of sight wind speeds u_{los} over the azimuth angle ϑ from range interval 3000 m to 3500 m (scattered markers) showing the applied methodology to derive wind direction differences. Cosine fits to all data (black line) to derive the global wind direction and to the data subsets north (blue \times and line) and south (orange \circ and line). Fit maxima, i.e. wind directions are marked with dashed lines. The overlapping region for the data of $\pm 10^\circ$ fits around the mean wind direction is visible by overlaid markers \times and \circ . The different amplitudes of the sector fits and the fit to the whole data are discussed in Sect. 4.

Figure 4: Difference between the VAD-reconstructed wind direction in the southerly respectively northerly sector and the global wind direction $\chi_{\text{global},r}$ dependent on range r and averaged over all lidar scans. The standard error of the mean is visualized as error bars.

larger ranges the wind is observed on a scale similar to the farm dimensions and in a far region without an influence of single turbines. The arcs of the far lidar range gates span from the upstream wind farm centre line to the wind farm boundaries. In contrast, for the near range gates the observed scale tends

more to the size of a single turbine with increasing influence of single wind turbine blockage. Further, the comparably small measurement arcs of the short ranges are located in front of the farm's centre (see Fig. 2). In this location no strong lateral flow components are expected.

The VAD method using a cosine fit to detect wind direction and speed is based on the assumption of homogeneous flow conditions. We found a lateral flow deflection due to the GBE. The wind speed taken as the amplitude of the fitted cosine deviates significantly from the measured wind speed values around the fit's maximum (see black global fit in Fig. 3). This highlights the importance for a careful application of the VAD method.

5 Conclusions

We analysed lidar data from an offshore wind farm in 79 global blockage situations on diverging wind direction in the inflow. We found the wind to be deflected towards both sides. In contrast, no wind direction changes were found in non-GBE situations, i.e. with no wind speed deficits upstream (not shown here). We conclude that GBE causes lateral flow deflections along with upstream wind speed differences. Further, we show that long-range Doppler lidar is a suitable tool to measure small effects on large scales like GBE. More comprehensive lidar campaigns in dual Doppler configuration are required to measure a more detailed flow field including wind speed and direction.

Free field observations of GBE are rare so far and focused mainly on upstream wind speed deficits. Free field observations of crosswise and vertical flow components should complement stream-wise wind speed measurements to enable more accurate tuning of engineering GBE models.

Acknowledgments

We acknowledge the wind farm operator Global Tech I Offshore Wind GmbH for the support of the measurement campaign. This work is partly funded by the Federal Ministry for Economics Affairs and Climate Action on the basis of a decision by the German Bundestag (OWP Control, grant no. 0324131A; X-Wakes, grant no. 03EE3008D; C²Wakes, grant no. 03EE3087B) and the EU project FLOW (grant agreement ID 101084205). We thank Gabriele Centurelli for fruitful discussions.

References

- [1] Porté-Agel F, Bastankhah M and Shamsoddin S 2019 *Boundary-Layer Meteorology* **174** 1–59
- [2] Schneemann J, Rott A, Dörenkämper M, Steinfeld G and Kühn M 2020 *Wind Energy Science* **5** 29–49
- [3] Lanzilao L and Meyers J 2022 *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* **2265** 022043
- [4] Strickland J M and Stevens R J 2022 *European Journal of Mechanics - B/Fluids* **95** 303–314
- [5] Lanzilao L and Meyers J 2024 *Journal of Fluid Mechanics* **979** A54
- [6] Gomez M S, Lundquist J K, Mirocha J D and Arthur R S 2023 *Wind Energy Science* **8** 1049–1069
- [7] Bleeg J, Purcell M, Ruisi R and Traiger E 2018 *Energies* **11** 1609
- [8] Schneemann J, Theuer F, Rott A, Dörenkämper M and Kühn M 2021 *Wind Energy Science* **6** 521–538
- [9] Carbon Trust and RWE Offshore Wind Accelerator (OWA): Setting the benchmark for measuring and assessing the global blockage effect. URL https://ctprodstorageaccountp.blob.core.windows.net/prod-drupal-files/documents/resource/public/GloBE%20Joint_Statement.pdf
- [10] Carbon Trust and RWE Measuring the global blockage effect URL https://ctprodstorageaccountp.blob.core.windows.net/prod-drupal-files/documents/resource/public/OWA_GloBE_Webinar1_Measurements.pdf
- [11] Carbon Trust and RWE Modelling and accounting for wake and blockage effects URL https://ctprodstorageaccountp.blob.core.windows.net/prod-drupal-files/documents/resource/public/OWA_GloBE_Webinar2_Modelling.pdf
- [12] Hasager C B, Nygaard N G and Poulos G S 2023 *Energies* **16** 8014
- [13] Rott A, Schneemann J, Theuer F, Quintero J J T and Kühn M 2022 *Wind Energy Science* **7** 283–297